

Mouse DN

Hodgin et al.

Human DN

Ju et al.

Woroniecka et al.

Type 1

Type 2

Gene	Primer	Sequence
MCP-1	Forward	TCACTGAAGCCAGCTCTCTCT
	Reverse	GTGGGGCGTTAACTGCAT
GAPDH	Forward	TGTCCGTCGTGGATCTGAC
	Reverse	CCTGCTTCACCACCTTCTTG
II-6	Forward	CCAGTTGCCTTCTTGGGACT
	Reverse	GGTCTGTTGGGAGTGGTATCC
TNFα	Forward	GCCTCTTCTCATTCTGCTTG
	Reverse	CTGATGAGAGGGAGGCCATT
SERPINE2	Forward	CAGTGTGAAGTGCAGAATGTGA
	Reverse	TTGGGGAAAGCAGATTATCAA
VEGF	Forward	CCTTCGTCCTCTCCTTACCC
	Reverse	AAGCCACTCACACACACAGC
MDK	Forward	CACCTCCAAGACCAAGTCAAA
	Reverse	CAAAAGGCACTGGTGGGTTA

Supplemental Figure 1: PN-1 glomerular expression

PN-1 glomerular expression data were extracted from the Nephroseq database (<https://www.nephroseq.org/resource/main.html>). Mouse data were from Hodgkin et al. Diabetes 2013;62(1):299-308. Human data were from Woroniecka KI, et al. Diabetes 2011 60(9):2354-69 and Wenjun J, Genome Res . 2013 Nov;23(11):1862-73.

Supplemental Figure 2 : Physiologic characteristics of mice

Body weight and blood glucose from: **A and B**: STZ-induced type 1 diabetic mice ; n = 8 to 12. **B and C**: db/db type diabetice mice ; n= 4 to 8.